

1 Use of remote sensing techniques to infer the Red Globe grape variety in the 2 Chancay-Lambayeque Valley (Northern Peru)

3 4 **Abstract**

5 Hitherto, it is essential to ensure sustainable crop production to carry out adequate control of
6 agricultural yields. Remote sensing plays a pivotal role in this context, as it not only enhances the
7 monitoring of crop growth but also optimizes the accuracy of yield predictions. For this reason,
8 in this study has been used remote sensing and GIS techniques to predict red globe variety yield
9 on four field plot trials, carried out on Lambayeque department, (three in Pátapo district and one
10 in Chongoyape district) with drip irrigation in an agricultural area located in the Chacay-
11 Lambayeque Valley at Northern of Peru. To carry out this work, a total of 423 satellite imageries
12 (138 Landsat 8 OLI, 218 Sentinel 2 L2A and 67 Landsat 7 ETM+) were acquired during the study
13 period (from November 1st 2018 up to December 10th 2021). During the harvest dates, December
14 and June of each year, the yield data (kg ha⁻¹) per plot were correlated with the dry matter
15 production data (kg ha⁻¹), resulting in a KNN based algorithm capable of predicting yield ($r =$
16 0.91 ; $R^2 = 0.969$; $p \leq 0.05$). In order to check the accuracy of red globe grape variety yield
17 estimates, authors analyzed the data collected by satellite imageries and finding that the difference
18 between the predicted and actual yield values was between 0.07 and 6.03%. Results of this study
19 revealed a considerable variation in field productivity, between December (mean value of 10250
20 kg ha⁻¹) and June (mean value of 8500 kg ha⁻¹), as a consequence of the El Niño phenomenon. It
21 was also observed that the relationship between grape yield and the assessed indices (GNDVI,
22 HDMI, and dry matter) exhibited a weak correlation for HDMI, high for GNDVI, and very high
23 for dry matter. In conclusion, it has been demonstrated that combining KNN and Correction
24 Algorithm (CA) resulted in more precise yield estimation.
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26 **Keywords**

27 Crop yield prediction; KNN; Lambayeque department; Remote sensing techniques; Red Globe
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31 1. Introduction

32 As it is well known, farmers aim to optimize crop yields while minimizing expenses. Detecting
33 issues that could impact crop production early on is essential for preventing costly errors and
34 maximizing profits. Grapes crops are recognized worldwide for their significance, and this
35 recognition is continually expanding. As interest in vineyard cultivation continues to rise, there is
36 a growing demand for improved crop protection and increased germplasm yield (Omomowo and
37 Babalola, 2021). The early detection of potential problems and the potential profitability of a
38 project can be very useful for marketing and pre-harvest decisions. Unfortunately, traditional
39 methods of estimating crop yield can lead to inaccurate and costly assessments. In addition, these
40 methods usually rely on field data collection, which is a time-consuming and costly process.
41 Vineyard yield prediction prior to harvest can be very useful in pre-harvest and marketing
42 decision making. Several research studies (Ali et al., 2019a; Basso and Liu, 2019) have
43 contended that conventional approaches for estimating crop yields and appraising crop
44 areas may yield imprecise results. Moreover, these methods typically hinge on meticulous
45 data gathering in the field regarding crops and their yields, a process that is both costly
46 and time-intensive.

48 As it is well known, remote sensing and global positioning system technologies can be used to
49 assess crop dynamics, such as crop yield and spatial variability (Muruganantham et al., 2022).
50 Visible (blue, green, and red) and near-infrared (NIR) portions of the electromagnetic spectrum
51 have already been shown to be effective in obtaining information on crop type, crop health, soil
52 moisture, nitrogen stress, and crop yield (Abbas et al., 2020; Arunrat et al., 2022; Barzin, 2021;
53 Cui et al., 2019; Fang et al., 2019) among other.

55 With advancements in remote sensing techniques, multispectral images have become an effective
56 tool for determining and monitoring vegetation conditions, crop stress, and crop yield prediction.
57 According to Karthikeyan et al., (2020), remote sensing data provided exceptional spatial and
58 temporal land surface characteristics, including environmental impacts on crop growth.
59 Numerous studies have found a strong relationship between the vegetation indices provided by
60 remote sensing techniques and crop yield and biomass (Karthikeyan et al., 2020; Lu et al., 2020).
61 Crop yield research at the regional scale, using coarse or low-resolution satellite images, can
62 provide more information on crop canopy conditions and crop yield estimates. As a result,
63 quantitative decisions on product export and import within the region could be made with
64 confidence.

66 Crop yield prediction is typically associated with specific agronomic variables (density, vigor,
67 maturity, and disease) that can be used as yield indicators. Remote sensing provides a close
68 diagnosis of plant health; however, crop spectral reflectance is affected by phenology, stage type,
69 and crop health. Several studies (Ali et al., 2019b; Gili et al., 2021; Kayad et al., 2019) have
70 focused on crop growth analysis using NDVI to improve precision agriculture. Plant life
71 monitoring research has shown that NDVI is related to the leaf area index (LAI) and crop
72 photosynthetic activity. Through its quasi-straight line relationship with the Fraction of Absorbed
73 Photosynthetically Active Radiation (fAPAR), the NDVI is an indirect way of measuring primary
74 productivity (Gao et al., 2021; Mansourmoghaddam et al., 2023; Rousta et al., 2022; Solano et
75 al., 2019). Also, Ali et al. (2019b) used Landsat ETM+ (Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus) data
76 with an NDVI model to estimate crop yield, with a yield prediction error ranging from 0.5 to 5.6
77 percent. Ali et al. (2021) predicted rice yield using Sentinel-2 data and the leaf area index, with a
78 95% accuracy.

80 Regarding vineyards, the use of remote sensing has given rise to variable yield predictions
81 depending on the methodology used. Ballesteros et al. (2020) used unmanned aerial vehicles
82 (UAVs) to obtain vegetation indices, which were related, through artificial neural networks, to
83 the yield obtained in the trials carried out in vineyards. The result was a model whose relative
84 error varied between 12.1% and 28.7%. Other authors (Arab et al., 2021) managed to relate the

85 existing information in the pixels of satellite images, through the use of machine learning
86 (Aghighi et al., 2018), with the NDVI time-series information of the study area, obtaining a linear
87 model capable of predicting the vineyard yield with a high precision ($R^2 = 0.79$). Similarly (Sun
88 et al., 2017), and through satellite remote sensing, daily LAI and NDVI have been used to infer
89 vineyard yield, reporting yield prediction values with relative errors between 6.9% and 11.5%.

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91 Despite the number of existing studies to date, related to the yield prediction in vineyards through
92 the use of remote sensing, none of them take into account variables that incorporate pruning wood,
93 a factor of great importance, since its quantification through of the Ravaz index (Pisciotta et al.,
94 2021a) allows us to know the relationship between the kilos of pruning wood necessary to produce
95 one kilo of grapes. For this reason, it is necessary highlighting this study aims to be innovative,
96 since even though it is difficult to find growers who weigh the pruned wood, it is true that this
97 can be quantified as part of the dry matter of the vineyard after pruning, which gives rise to a
98 greater precision when obtaining vineyard yields. This has never been used in any previous
99 research study, and this is precisely a contribution to knowledge of enormous importance given
100 the increase in yield precision estimation that it gives rise to for any type of crop, regardless of
101 the geographical area.

102 103 **2. Materials and Methods**

104 **2.1. Study area**

105 The Chancay-Lambayeque valley, like others along the Peruvian coast, receives no rain
106 throughout the year. The Tinajones dam regulates irrigation for the entire valley's agriculture. The
107 dam has improved the availability of water supply since its construction, though it is still a very
108 scarce resource. Water scarcity manifests itself in two ways in general. To begin, despite the
109 availability of irrigation, farmers are forced to reduce their production even further during drought
110 years. Second, irrigation water competes with domestic water use, and according to Carmona De
111 La Cruz (2020), total rural demand is not met.

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113 Furthermore, the region is extremely vulnerable to extreme weather events such as droughts and
114 floods, which are linked to the El Niño Southern Oscillation phenomenon. The previous El Niño
115 event had a negative impact on agriculture, reducing Gross Domestic Product (GDP) by 13% and
116 damaging many types of infrastructure, among other things. Similarly, it should be noted that the
117 Chancay-Lambayeque valley is extremely vulnerable to climate change. As a result, changes in
118 precipitation are expected to exacerbate water shortages in the Basin. Furthermore, as a result of
119 deforestation, the system's capacity to capture rainwater has decreased, while deforestation has
120 made it more vulnerable to flooding (Altamirano, 2021).

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122 On the other hand, it is necessary to specify that this study was carried out in Pátapo and
123 Chongoyape districts (Fig. 1 and 2), one of the main grape growing area in Chiclayo province
124 (Lambayeque, Peru). Table grapes, in 2020, make up about 2% of the overall primary crops
125 production in Peru (FAO, 2022).

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127 In that same year (2020), the vineyard surface was 35,159 ha with 733,610 tons of total
128 production, and 208655 kg per hectare of average per vineyard yield in all country. At level of
129 the Lambayeque department, it is important to specify that the increase in grape area in recent
130 years has been possible thanks to the policy of productive offer diversification initiated by the
131 local government in 2008 (Central Reserve Bank of Peru, 2008). Despite the fact that in the
132 Lambayeque department, agricultural activity has historically been developed based on the
133 sowing of four crops (rice, sugar cane, cotton and hard yellow corn), the incorporation of grape
134 cultivation has made possible, according to the National Institute of Statistics and Informatics
135 (National Institute of Statistics and Informatics (NISI), 2022, 2021, 2020) of Peru, a percentage
136 increase of production at national level, between the years 2019 and 2022, as shown in
137 Table 1.

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According to Peruvian Government (2022), and taking into account table grape exports, it should be noted that, in 2021, Peru positioned itself as the main exporter of fresh grapes. In that year, Peruvian exports reached a total of 1260 million American dollars, with an increase of 22% compared to 2020. Among the main geographical areas to which Peru exports its grape production, it is worth mentioning the United States, the European Union, Hong Kong, the United Kingdom, Mexico, China and South Korea (Peruvian Government, 2022).

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Figure 1. Location of both Lambayeque department and Chiclayo province. Source: Authors.

Figure 2. Location of Chongoyape and Pátapo districts and the plot trials. Source: Authors.

Regarding the climate of Pátapo and Chongoyape, and according to Climate-data.org (2022) it should be noted that Pátapo has a desert climate, type BWh according to the Köppen-Geiger classification. Its average annual temperature is 21.6 °C, while its precipitation is 208 mm per year. On the other hand, Chongoyape has a local steppe climate, type BSh according to the Köppen-Geiger classification, with an average annual temperature of 21.3 °C and annual rainfall of 527 mm. These climatic characteristics make it possible for table grapes, and specifically the Red Globe variety, to be produced under favorable conditions.

Table 1. Percentage variation of grape production in Peru between January 2019 and January 2022.

Date	Percentage change
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Jan. 2019 to Jan. 2020	25.45
Jan. 2020 to Jan. 2021	28.68
Jan. 2021 to Jan. 2022	10.47

2.2. Data acquisition

The spectral datasets were collected from Landsat 8 OLI (Operational Land Imager), Sentinel 2 MSI L2A (Multi-Spectral Instrument Level-2A product) and Landsat 7 ETM+ (Enhance Thematic Mapper Plus) time series for 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2021. The OLI sensor consists of a total of nine spectral bands with a spatial resolution of 30 m for bands 2 to 4 (RGB), 1, 6, 7 and 9. Band 1 is useful for coastal and aerosol studies. Bands 7 and 6 are shortwave infrared (SWIR) and are useful for water detection of vegetation and water bodies, and band 9 is cirrus, which can be useful for cloud detection. Landsat 8 spatial and temporal scenes were obtained and referred from OLI/TIRS C1 level-1 with path 010 and rows 064 and 065.

Regarding the MSI sensor of the Sentinel 2 satellite, it must be pointed out that it has thirteen spectral bands with a resolution of 10 m (bands 2, 3, 4 “RGB” and 8 “VNIR”), 20 m (bands 5, 6, 7, 8a “VNIR”, 11 and 12 “SWIR”) or 60 m (bands 1 “coastal and aerosol”, 9 and 10 “SWIR”). All images obtained by this sensor from the Sentinel 2 satellite are in the 17MPN military grid (used by NATO).

Finally, the ETM+ sensor of the Landsat 7 satellite has a total of six spectral bands with a resolution of 30 m (bands 1, 2, 3 "RGB", 4 "NIR", 5 and 7 "SWIR"). All images from this sensor are located at path 010 and row 065.

All Landsat 8 OLI, Sentinel 2 MSI L2A and Landsat 7 ETM+ series scenes were directly downloaded from USGS EarthExplorer website, and entire growth cycles over four years were obtained from a total of 423 processed scenes (138 from Landsat 8, 218 from Sentinel 2 and 67 from Landsat 7).

Subsequently, and with the use of the Ilwis Geographic Information System (GIS), all the images were improved. Subsequently, using the nearest neighbor algorithm, it was possible to keep the original brightness of the pixel values unchanged, according to Ramírez-Juidías and Yanes-Figueroa (2017).

In another vein, due to the importance of the Ravaz index in grapes (Pisciotta et al., 2021b), it is evident that there is a relationship between dry matter and the final production of table grapes. For this reason, we proceeded to obtain an algorithm that would allow us to infer the kilos of dry matter per hectare, to later calculate the yield predictor algorithm in the test plots (Fig. 3).

As a result of the importance of the vine development in the different phenological stages, it was of enormous importance to know for sure the chlorophyll-producing capacity of the plant over time. For this reason, and according to (Astaoui et al., 2021), the Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (GNDVI) has been taken into account to obtain the dry matter per hectare. Similarly, due to the negative correlation between dry matter and its water content (Gao, 1996), it was decided to use the Humidity Difference Moisture Index (HDMI). Given that the GNDVI (Eq. [1]) is the existing relation, between the difference and the sum, of the NIR and green (G) bands, and that the HDMI (Eq. [2]) is the relation, also between the difference and the sum, of the NIR and SWIR1 bands, in Table 2 the spectral bands corresponding to those mentioned for each of the satellites used in this study are shown.

Table 2. Spectral bands corresponding to NIR, SWIR1 and green (G) for the three satellites used.

Spectral band	Sentinel 2 MSI L2A	Landsat 8 OLI	Landsat 7 ETM+
NIR	B08	B5	B4
SWIR1	B11	B6	B5
G	B03	B3	B2

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$$GNDVI = \frac{NIR - G}{NIR + G} \quad [1]$$

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$$HDMI = \frac{NIR - SWIR1}{NIR + SWIR1} \quad [2]$$

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214 As is known, according to García Cárdenas et al. (2019), the use of G band in the GNDVI is
 215 related to the radiation proportion absorbed photosynthetically and is linearly correlated with the
 216 leaf area index (LAI). Accordingly, GNDVI is more sensitive to chlorophyll concentration than
 217 NDVI. On the other hand, HDMI is used to monitor changes in water content of leaves (Gao,
 218 1996).

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220 Figure 3 shows the flowchart followed in this study.

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Figure 3. Flowchart for yield prediction of Red Globe variety. Source: Authors.

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225 2.3. Data analysis

226 Regarding the statistical analysis, it is important to specify that in order to establish the different
227 stages of growth in Red Globe vineyard, we used two methods: per-pixel moving average and
228 exponential smoothing. Once we identified the different stages, we conducted an analysis to
229 examine the connections between the GNDVI and HDMI. Later, a model was created using a
230 time-series moving average method to remove variations in active growing seasons and get one
231 representative mean score for each model. Regression analyses were then performed to investigate
232 the relationship between the scores obtained from this model (GNDVI and HDMI during active
233 growing seasons) with the ground reference yield. As is known, the moving average can be
234 expressed as follows (Eq. [3]):
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$$236 \quad Mav_n = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n IV_i}{n} \quad [3]$$

237 where “Mav” is the moving average, “IV” is the independent variable (GNDVI, HDMI and dry
238 matter) in period “i”, and “n” is the number of periods. The method for determining the predictions
239 of GNDVI, HDMI and dry matter is outlined in Eq. [4]:
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$$242 \quad P_t = \beta \cdot OV_{t-1} + (1 - \beta) \cdot P_{t-1} \quad [4]$$

243 where “ P_t ” is the prediction of independent variable for month “t”, “ β ” is a smoothing constant,
244 “ OV_{t-1} ” is the observed value of GNDVI, HDMI and dry matter in each Red Globe vineyard in
245 period “t”, and “ P_{t-1} ” is the previous prediction to the period “t”.
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248 Another approach in addition to the use of a parametric method was employed for identifying the
249 most effective method for predicting yield, which was nonparametric technique. The K-Nearest
250 Neighbors (KNN) model was chosen for this situation because it can handle both linear and highly
251 complex relationships between the input and output data (as shown in Figure 4).
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Figure 4. K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm, along with Correction Algorithm (CA), for predicting Red Globe variety grape yield. Source: Authors.

The k-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm is a type of instance-based learning or non-parametric classification algorithm. It can be used for both classification and regression problems. The basic idea behind the KNN algorithm is to find the k-number of closest points in the feature space for a new data point, and then predict the label of the new point based on the majority label of those closest points. In practice, the algorithm works as follows: 1.- Store all the training examples in the memory; 2.- When a new point is encountered, calculate the distance between that point and all the stored points; 3.- Select the k-points which are closest to the new point; 4.- Output the most common label among those k-points as the prediction for the new point. It is important to highlight that the KNN is a simple algorithm and easy to implement. Also, it is sensitive to the choice of k, the number of nearest neighbors to consider, and to the distance metric used to measure the similarity between the points.

Based on what is indicated in Figure 4, the Correction Algorithm (CA) used for estimating the value of test point by weighted average of its neighbor is presented below (Eq. [5]):

$$AP + \left[\frac{H_{ss}}{\log_{10}\left(\left(\frac{fAPAR}{AP}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{P_{KNN}}}\right)\right)} \right] \pm |AP - P_{KNN}| \quad [5]$$

where “AP” is the average production, in kg per hectare, of each test plot, either in December or in June. “ H_{ss} ” is the soil surface moisture, as a percentage, inferred from daily data obtained with the Crop Monitoring application, and dependent on the relative humidity “RH (%)”, the precipitation “ P (mm/day)” and the mean temperature “ T_{av} (°C)” at plot level, as shown in Eq. [6]. Regarding “fAPAR” (Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation) variable, comment that it has been obtained through the PROVA-V sensor (daily data at 300 m resolution). On the other hand, “ P_{KNN} ” is the production, in kg per hectare, obtained by the KNN model before applying the Correction Algorithm (CA) specified in Eq. [5] (see Figure 4). Finally, it is necessary to specify, in reference to the \pm sign of Eq. [5], that the positive value will be used when “ P_{KNN} ” is greater than “AP”, and the negative value otherwise ($P_{KNN} < AP$).

$$H_{ss}(\%) = 19.41 + 0.13 \cdot RH + 1.23 \cdot P + 0.12 \cdot T_{av} \quad (R^2 = 0.965; r = 0.78; p \leq 0.05) \quad [6]$$

Data on vineyard management was gathered through a survey to investigate the agronomic practices related to handling pest outbreaks, droughts, and floods.

3. Results and Discussion

As is well known, the development stages of table grapes are recognized as: bud break (when small buds on the vine start to expand and green leaves start to show), flowering (when grapevine flowers form in clusters, blooming when temperatures reach 15-20 °C, 6-9 weeks after bud break), fruit set (rapid growth period due to cell division and enlargement, green and hard grape berries with little sugar and high organic acids (Goldammer, 2015), maximum canopy expansion, ripening, and harvesting. To determine these growth stages in vineyards, growth trajectories were created using moving average and exponential smoothing methods.

A four-year sequence of GNDVI, HDMI, and dry matter data (2018-2021) was used. Seasonality was removed from the GNDVI, HDMI, and dry matter dataset time-series (Fig. 5 and 6). Black points, existing in Figures 5 and 6, represent the time-series GNDVI, HDMI and dry matter values of each field test during 1285 study days, the blue points refer to exponential smoothing and the orange points represent the moving average.

In the same way, and with the purpose of verifying the existence of significant differences between field plot trials, for the different years of this study (2018, 2019, 2020 y 2021), in relation to the time-series GNDVI, HDMI and dry matter, in Table 3 is shown the mean values of each of them, while Table 4 is shown the compare means results.

Figure 5. GNDVI and HDMI time-series in 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2021 (1285 study days in each field plot trial).

Source: Authors.

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Figure 6. Dry matter time-series in 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2021 (1285 study days in each field plot trial). Source: Authors.

As can be seen in Table 3, the GNDVI values corresponding to the Pátapo field plots (field plot trial 2, 3 and 4) are very similar, as is the case with the HDMI values. However, when comparing the GNDVI values of Pátapo and Chongoyape (field plot trial 1), significant differences appear ($p \leq 0.05$). This may be due to the influence, on the vegetation development, of the climate type existing in each district (BWh in Pátapo and BSh in Chongoyape according to the Köppen-Geiger classification), and therefore, to a greater chlorophyll production (García Cárdenas et al., 2019) in the Red Globe vineyards of Chongoyape, which would explain a higher GNDVI in the field plot trial 1. Regarding the values of dry matter, and HDMI, in Table 3 it can be observed that there are no differences between districts. This is logical, not only because the different producers have followed the same cultivation practices (Table 5) under gravity irrigation, but also because both variables are related to the different growth stages and development of the Red Globe variety, which can also be seen in Figures 5 and 6.

Table 3. Time-series GNDVI, HDMI and dry matter mean values for each field plot trial (DM* = dry matter in kg per hectare).

Year	Field plot trial 1			Field plot trial 2			Field plot trial 3			Field plot trial 4		
	GNDVI	HDMI	DM*	GNDVI	HDMI	DM*	GNDVI	HDMI	DM*	GNDVI	HDMI	DM*
2018	0.36	0.07	9580	0.27	0.11	8681	0.29	0.13	9349	0.29	0.10	8909
2019	0.36	0.07	9598	0.36	0.13	10172	0.36	0.13	10111	0.36	0.13	10251
2020	0.34	0.08	8164	0.37	0.12	9545	0.40	0.09	10548	0.40	0.14	10385
2021	0.31	0.09	8942	0.29	0.10	8235	0.31	0.12	9162	0.32	0.14	10159
2018	0.36	0.07	9580	0.27	0.11	8681	0.29	0.13	9349	0.29	0.10	8909
2019	0.36	0.07	9598	0.36	0.13	10172	0.36	0.13	10111	0.36	0.13	10251

Table 4. Compare means test between Field Plot Trials (FPT) ($p \leq 0.05$ = significant differences less than 5 %; n.s. = no significant differences).

	GNDVI	HDMI	Dry matter
FPT 1 vs FPT 2	$p \leq 0.05$	n.s.	n.s.
FPT 1 vs FPT 3	$p \leq 0.05$	n.s.	n.s.
FPT 1 vs FPT 4	$p \leq 0.05$	n.s.	n.s.
FPT 2 vs FPT 3	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
FPT 2 vs FPT 4	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
FPT 3 vs FPT 4	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

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Table 5. Island guano (in kg/ha) fertilization dates, in all field plot trials (clay-loam soil) based on phenology from Red Globe vineyards.

Years	Sprouting (100 kg/ha)	Fruit set (150 kg/ha)	Bunch development (150 kg/ha)
2018	February, 18	March, 20	April, 24
	July, 16	August, 17	September, 19
2019	February, 18	March, 21	April, 24
	July, 17	August, 16	September, 20
2020	February, 16	March, 20	April, 21
	July, 18	August, 21	September, 21
2021	February, 18	March, 25	April, 24
	July, 19	August, 20	September, 22

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In another vein, and with regard to the yield estimation in the study area, in Eq. [7] is shown how to infer the crop yield (kg/ha) from dry matter (kg/ha). It is important to highlight that the algorithm shown in Eq. [7] is not local, since its direct dependence on dry matter makes it possible for the vineyard to have more or less production based on the Ravaz index (Pisciotta et al., 2021a).

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$$Yield_{Estimated} = 13139.4 - 0.26 \cdot Dry\ matter \quad (r = 0.91; R^2 = 0.969; p \leq 0.05) \quad [7]$$

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Knowing that in each of field plot trials, the first one harvest date was December 5, 2018 and the last one was December 10, 2021, in addition to the date corresponding to the harvest of the June month of each year was between the 5th and 8th of said month, there are a total of 28 real yield data and 28 estimated yield using Eq. [7] (See Table 6).

Table 6. Real vs estimated yield in each field plot trial.

Field Plot Trial	Harvest date	Real yield (kg/ha)	Estimated yield (kg/ha)
1	05/12/2018	10000	10200.15
	07/06/2019	8500	10001.22
	04/12/2019	9000	10767.29
	05/06/2020	8500	9537.07
	06/12/2020	12000	10070.65
	08/06/2021	8500	9195.19
	10/12/2021	10000	9207.03
2	05/12/2018	10000	11652.76
	07/06/2019	8500	9024.62
	04/12/2019	9000	9470.04
	05/06/2020	8500	7473.36
	06/12/2020	12000	12335.30
	08/06/2021	8500	10805.69
	10/12/2021	10000	9836.40
3	05/12/2018	10000	10851.01
	07/06/2019	8500	9489.27
	04/12/2019	9000	8703.11
	05/06/2020	8500	8671.98
	06/12/2020	12000	10089.43
	08/06/2021	8500	8992.16
	10/12/2021	10000	10149.79
4	05/12/2018	10000	10200.15
	07/06/2019	8500	10001.22
	04/12/2019	9000	10767.29
	05/06/2020	8500	9537.07
	06/12/2020	12000	10070.65
	08/06/2021	8500	9195.19
	10/12/2021	10000	9207.03

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Table 6 shows that the estimated yield values are very similar to those of the real yield using the complete sample (all field plot trials data). For this reason, in order to check the validity of the

model used in Eq. [7], it was decided to carry out a compare mean test between the real and the estimated yield, which did not show significant differences neither in t-test nor in F-test (see Table 7).

Table 7. Compare mean test between real yield and estimated yield in all field plot trials. Source: Authors.

Data summary					
	Real yield (sample A)		Estimated yield (sample B)		Total
n	28		28		56
$\sum x$	266,000		271,619		537,619
$\sum x^2$	2,567,000,000		2,678,014,063		5,245,014,063
Squares sum	40,000,000		43,125,450.1		83,689,256.5
Mean	9,500		9,700.7786		9,600.3393
t-test assuming equal sample variances. (Applicable only to independent samples)					
Mean_A – Mean_B	t	df	P	one-tailed	0.27221
-200.6786	-0.61	54		two-tailed	0.544420
F-test for the significance of the difference between the variances of the two samples					
	df₁	df₂	F	P	
	27	27	1.08	0.421490	
P>0.05 indicates no significant difference detected between the variances of the two samples. (Applicable only to independent samples)					
t-test assuming unequal sample variances. (Applicable only to independent samples)					
Mean_A – Mean_B	t	df	P	one-tailed	0.2737925
-200.6786	-0.61	53.92		two-tailed	0.547585
Confidence intervals					
	Observed	0.95		0.99	
Mean_A	9,500	± 471.5448		± 637.1605	
Mean_B	9,700.6786	± 489.6207		± 661.5851	
Mean_A – Mean_B (assuming equal sample variances)	-200.6786	± 663.1872		± 885.3548	
Mean_A – Mean_B (assuming unequal sample variances)	-200.6786	± 663.1872		± 885.3548	

However, after comparing the real and estimated yield values in each field plot trial (Table 8), it was found that in the Chongoyape plot (FPT 1), as well as in FPT 4 (located in Pátapo), only significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) were found, after carrying out the F-test, between the variances of the two samples. This only means that, despite the fact that the null hypothesis must be rejected (for both field plot trial not all means are equal), from a practical point of view the model used in this study is useful, since it allows obtaining, at a local level, a good yield prediction through the relationship between the satellite spectral data and the real yield.

Table 8. Compare means test (F-test result) between real yield and estimated yield in each Field Plot Trials (FPT) (t-test assuming both equal and unequal sample variances have no significant differences neither one-tailed nor two-tailed; $p \leq 0.05$ = significant differences less than 5 %; n.s. = no significant differences).

	FPT 1	FPT 2	FPT 3	FPT 4
Yield	$p \leq 0.05$	n.s.	n.s.	$p \leq 0.05$

Table grapes are a highly perishable commodity and, for this reason, minimizing post-harvest losses through effective supply chain logistics is crucial. Yield prediction is a key factor in this

381 regard. In this study, a model was developed to predict Red Globe table grape yields using
382 machine learning techniques and various indices based on satellite remote sensing, such as
383 GNDVI, HDMI and dry matter. Certain growth stages were found to be particularly significant,
384 such as ripening mainly, in evaluating vineyard variability during the growing season. The
385 vineyard-based growth stages of table grapes were determined using Sentinel 2, Landsat 8, and
386 Landsat 7 datasets. It was observed that, in accordance with the crop calendar, the vine vigor
387 decreased and the grape berries reached the final stage of ripening about 30 days before harvest.
388 Additionally, remote sensing indices like GNDVI, HDMI and dry matter were identified as crucial
389 parameters that can provide near-real-time information on canopy development, crop calendar,
390 water stress, plant health, and grape yield.

391

392 Predicting grape yield is a difficult task due to the many environmental and field management
393 factors involved, making it challenging to establish a single grape yield prediction model based
394 on remotely sensed data (see Fig. 7, 8 and 9). In this study, the correlations between yield and
395 maximum indices were examined for each month, and it was found that the correlation between
396 grape yield and the studied indices (GNDVI, HDMI, and dry matter) was low for HDMI ($r =$
397 0.296 and $R^2 = 0.08$), high for GNDVI ($r = 0.884$ and $R^2 = 0.781$), and very high for dry matter
398 ($r = 0.91$ and $R^2 = 0.969$), as shown in Figures 10, 11, and 12. A time-series moving average was
399 used to represent all growth stages, which yielded better results than other methods. The study's
400 results indicated that dry matter was the most accurate in the machine-learning approach for all
401 four years, accounting for nearly 97% of the variability in 1285 study days, and the predicted
402 yields from dry matter had RMSE values listed in Table 9.

403

Yield maps of FPT 1

Figure 7. Estimated yield maps of FPT 1 obtained through remote sensing. Source: Authors.

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Yield maps of FPT 2

Yield maps of FPT 3

Figure 8. Estimated yield maps of FPT 2 and FPT 3 obtained through remote sensing. Source: Authors.

Yield maps of FPT 4

Figure 9. Estimated yield maps of FPT 4 obtained through remote sensing. Source: Authors.

Table 9. RMSE values (in kg/ha) by FPT.

	FPT 1	FPT 2	FPT 3	FPT 4
RMSE (December)	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.05
RMSE (June)	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.03
RMSE (June + December)	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.04
RMSE_{total}	0.02			

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Figure 10. Relationship between the estimated yield (kg/ha) and HDMI using regression analysis. Source: Authors.

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Figure 11. Relationship between the estimated yield (kg/ha) and GNDVI using regression analysis. Source: Authors.

Figure 12. Relationship between the estimated yield (kg/ha) and dry matter (kg/ha) using regression analysis. Source: Authors.

It is evident that in order to increase the model accuracy, increasing the size of the data set, including more predictor variables, and using time-series data with shorter revisit cycles are essential. The main constraint in this research was the absence of more seasonal datasets from field observations, which is due to a lack of resources and field security. However, four years of ground reference yield prediction datasets along with satellite remote sensing data could help the local government and stakeholders develop a better marketing strategy to decrease pre- and postharvest losses of grapes.

4. Conclusions

In the present study, it is the first time that dry matter is used as the only main variable to predict vineyard yield.

GNDVI, HDMI, and dry matter were found as efficacious parameters in the prediction of table grape yield across varying growth phases. To remove the time series seasonality and determine the growth trajectory and production stages of table grapes, moving average and exponential smoothing methods were used. It was discovered that the vine vigor decreased and the grape berries reached the final stage of ripening approximately 30 days before harvest, according to the crop calendar.

Satellite-based remote sensing was used to predict grape yield over the growing season, with GNDVI being the most accurate ($R^2 = 0.781$), followed by dry matter ($R^2 = 0.969$). HDMI is a positive covariate in the predictive model.

A machine learning approach based on K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) was implemented, and the outcomes demonstrated that integrating KNN with the Correction Algorithm (CA) yielded more accurate estimations of grape yield. This research presents a valuable model for gauging grape yield and producing spatially variable yield maps. Leveraging satellite-derived vegetation indices (GNDVI, HDMI, and dry matter) proved to be a resourceful and efficient method for anticipating table grape yield across diverse growth stages. This not only assists farmers in pinpointing optimal

455 harvesting times but also enhances stakeholder comprehension of the various grape growth stages,
456 facilitating site-specific management strategies.

457
458 Regarding the strengths of the model, it must be emphasized that the use in the correction
459 algorithm (CA), shown in Eq. [5,] of variables such as soil surface moisture " H_{ss} ", as well as
460 " $fAPAR$ " (Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation), makes it possible to take
461 into account vital factors for the vineyard development, which allow the model to have much
462 more precision than those existing to date.

463
464 As a limitation is the necessity of know, for each field plot trial, the historical average production
465 (kg/ha), at least from the previous three or five years.

466
467 Another limitation to the developed model, it must be commented that it has only been evaluated
468 for vineyard crop. For this reason, future work aims to apply it to other woody crops where dry
469 matter, as occurs in the vine, is related to increased yield through adequate pruning. Later, in a
470 second phase, it will be checked if it works for herbaceous crops.

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